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KLYMENCHUKOVA N.S.

Methodology of innovative entrepreneurship development in the period of crisis and bifurcations

Relevance of the research topic. *The challenge for modern innovative enterprises is not only the production of innovations, but also the optimization of production capacities and technological capabilities of fixed assets. This can be achieved by improving the management process or forming a fundamentally new enterprise management model, which leads to adaptive or revolutionary organizational changes that will increase business profitability.*

Formulation of the problem. *There is a need to form a methodological basis for the management behavior of innovatively active market stakeholders and to maximize its impact on the growth of labor productivity, efficiency and profitability of entrepreneurship, and the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage.*

Setting goals and objectives of the study – *to offer the author's methodology for the development of innovative entrepreneurship during crises.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the methods of monographic, abstraction, graphic, concretization, systematization, formalization, analysis, synthesis.*

Presentation of the main material (research results). *The author's methodology for the development of innovative entrepreneurship during crises is proposed. The key elements of the*

author's methodology are identified.

Scope of the results. The methodology for the development of innovative entrepreneurship during crises can be used by scientists and other market stakeholders who are interested in the issues of ensuring innovative activity.

Conclusions on the article. The author's methodology for the development of innovative entrepreneurship during crises is proposed. Its main elements and tools are considered.

Key words: methodology, tools, innovation, crises, entrepreneurship.

КЛИМЕНЧУКОВА Н.С.

Методологія розвитку інноваційного підприємництва в період криз та біфуркацій

Актуальність теми дослідження. Викликом для сучасних інноваційно активних підприємств є не лише продукування нововведень але й оптимізація виробничих потужностей та технологічних можливостей основних фондів. Зазначене можливо досягти через поліпшення процесу управління або формування принципово нової методології управління підприємством, що призводить до адаптаційних або революційних організаційних змін, які забезпечать підвищення прибутковості бізнесу.

Постановка проблеми. Існує потреба формування методологічного підґрунтя управлінської поведінки інноваційно активних стейкхолдерів ринку, та максимізації її впливу на зростання продуктивності праці, ефективності та прибутковості підприємництва, досягнення стійкої конкуренції переваги.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – запропонувати авторську методологію розвитку інноваційного підприємництва в період криз.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано методи монографічний, абстрагування, графічний, конкретизації, систематизації, формалізації, аналізу, синтезу.

Презентація основного матеріалу (результати дослідження). Запропоновано авторську методологію розвитку інноваційного підприємництва в період криз. Визначено ключові елементи авторської методології.

Галузь застосування результатів. Методологію розвитку інноваційного підприємництва в період криз можливо використовувати науковцям та іншим стейкхолдерами ринку, які зацікавлені проблематикою забезпечення інноваційної діяльності.

Висновки за статтею. Запропоновано авторську методологію розвитку інноваційного підприємництва в період криз. Розглянуто основні її елементи та інструменти.

Ключові слова: методологія, інструментарій, інноваційна діяльність, кризи, підприємництво.

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. The modern institutional environment in which entrepreneurship is characterized by constant variability, which requires more flexible management and adaptive intra-corporate behavior of the manager, who predicts the future and strives for continuous innovation through improved management. Such a management system involves improving the logic of doing business through the planning of new management practices, allocation and economical use of limited resources while stimulating innovative production and forming a flexible portfolio of services best for the competitor, achieving high financial and economic performance and

business results. This cannot be clearly spelled out in the medium or long term (given the rapid variability of the external environment), so there is a need to improve the methodology in the context of bridging the gap between previous research and current business challenges. The development of the methodology should build on the traditionally existing concepts of the model of market stakeholders, which have already been described within various economic schools, and on their basis determine the basic elements of the new methodology to ensure business success and increase its innovation.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, which initiated the solution of this problem and on which the author relies, highlighting

previously unsolved parts of the general problem, which is the subject of this article.

Most scientific theories indicate the importance of managerial innovation to ensure the business success of the enterprise [1–5; 7–11; 14]. Achieving maximization of the impact of such management concepts is possible through their gradual adjustments and updates to the modern realities of the national economy, which will lead to explicit and implicit changes in business, form new management practices, encourage managers to innovative way of doing business, leading to a wide diffusion of innovations. [6; 12–13; 15].

Formulation of the goals of the article (setting the task) – to offer the author’s methodology for the development of innovative entrepreneurship in times of crisis.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results.

Improving and actively implementing modern ways of doing business with a more effective ratio of both entrepreneurial and social utility, adjusts the trend of scientific research towards the discovery of a fundamentally new methodology for discussion. The need for such a change in research is the result of evolutions and transformations inherent in innovation-oriented enterprises, where market success is explained not only by technical knowledge and supply of know-how or technical and technological solutions, but also by successful business methodology, which is the key to effective management based on a combination of science, practice and business. Examining previous scientific research on the methodology of innovative business development, taking into account the variability of the external environment, there are different approaches to the perception of this phenomenon. A number of scholars proposing the methodology emphasize the need to change administrative, infrastructural and financial and economic conditions that stimulate the diffusion of innovation in entrepreneurship, while identifying factors that improve management methods and professional growth of managers through training or retraining. Such methodologies are based on the introduction of rapid tools to ensure the industrialization and technology of production in turbulent conditions and to adjust management behavior between managers and staff. The spread of such methodologies, in our opinion, leads to technologi-

cal revolutions, the formation of new ways of personnel management, based on the introduction of the author’s approach to management, accumulation of entrepreneurial capital, welfare, system resource rationalism as a challenge to adapt to the modern business environment. characterized by constant changes and a high degree of uncertainty.

Other authors emphasize the need to first form such a theoretical and methodological foundation for innovative development of entrepreneurship, which will radically change the existing organizational culture through the introduction of new management practices. In such studies, the authors point out the importance of stimulating the innovative and creative potential of the enterprise and the formation of the organizational foundation of business, which will ensure the survival and success of business without the need to change production as something superfluous and complex. The authors believe that changes in production will occur naturally to the challenges of the external environment with the lowest financial costs, if the organizational culture is optimal for this type of business. To succeed in this enterprise with such a methodology, it is necessary to provide the prerequisites, including:

- formation of a highly intelligent critical mass of managers at all levels of enterprise management with such innovative managerial behavior that will best realize their managerial roles;
- optimization of management functions by such managers (planning, organization, leadership, delegation and control) in order to ensure long-term business success and structuring of business processes, their review and elimination of those that limit or slow down the adaptation and development of the enterprise;
- systematic review of the existing organizational structure, especially in large budget-generating enterprises, because they are the sources of filling the budget, and their low efficiency affects the effectiveness of socio-economic development of territories and leads to deterioration of macroeconomic indicators across the country.

Without rejecting the importance of the authors’ scientific research, we believe that the solution to the problem of forming the methodology of institutional support for entrepreneurship in an innovative economy should be a combined approach using a set of elements, tools, methods and principles used in the author’s vision to solve the problem. Such a

Simplified scheme of implementation of the methodology of the mode of institutional support for the development of entrepreneurship in the innovative economy

Source: author's development

methodology should radically change not only the internal structure of the enterprise but also lead to the movement of external factors surrounding the enterprise. Such key concepts should be found in the methodology to most successfully transform the institutional environment into favorable for innovation, reduce its aggressiveness, increase the culture of managerial role of managers in order to deepen their ability to identify implicit or explicit incentives for innovation. In such a methodology, we must focus on the assimilation of powerful drivers of growth and development of innovation, ie radical changes at all stages of business development, innovative functioning of production and the formation of an effective institutional matrix. The main elements of the methodology are shown in Fig. 1.

Currently, the institutional environment and infrastructure of entrepreneurship in Ukraine is unfavorable, which reduces the innovation potential and diffusion of innovations in all enterprises, regardless of size and form of ownership. Entrepreneurs are trapped in an institutional trap and their innovative potential is not fully exploited. Even those companies that have this potential due to the negative impact of imperfect government policies and legislation

with gaps and conflicts, fail in the life cycle of creating innovation-oriented products or know-how. Businesses are struggling to change the business practices of their own activities through the resistance of the system. Only by implementing powerful, highly intelligent modern business approaches, managers are able to minimize the negative external influence on the current activities of the enterprise. That is why the new methodology should be based on the transformation of the external environment and the accumulation of the company's ability to adapt, so as to ensure the rapid spread of innovation and attract even more companies to innovation. This would allow to achieve positive results even in those enterprises that before the implementation of the methodology were characterized by inefficient rigid and management, burdened with great bureaucratic administrative pressure from outside. By giving them more adaptability and flexibility, which will ensure a long-term prospect of their survival in the market, even in the face of changing market conditions.

The opinions of researchers on this issue, the current market situation, the current business environment, the specifics of the innovative nature of large business, the peculiarities of medium and

small business, which should be carriers of economic growth and development allow us to determine the key principles of our methodology. It consists of improving the management of an innovative enterprise, increasing its profitability, ensuring uninterrupted growth with the progressive development of the institutional environment. In this context, there is a need to identify national success factors in order to provide incentives for innovation, especially in the areas needed to strengthen the country's food, military and social security. The methodology should be determined on the basis of observation of global innovation development, trends in management, public administration, European business experience, search for new knowledge in full compliance with the interests of entrepreneurs who create innovations.

Conclusions

Therefore, the organizational elements of the methodology must be implemented in different industries and in different markets, the activities of which can be described as variable–dynamic, complex, stably uncertain. Such a methodology should encourage changes in the organizational structure of the enterprise, the logic of management, the practice of successful management of the necessary changes and the maximum use of all opportunities for the survival of the enterprise in a crisis.

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